

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

D2.3 2ND YEAR EVALUATION REPORT ON QUESTIONNAIRES, DEVELOPED COURSES AND EVENTS

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Executive Summary

D2.3 2nd year evaluation report on questionnaires, developed courses and events

The report summarises the evaluation of activities conducted in the second year of the AGEMERA project within the Work Package (WP) 2. The evaluated activities are confined to developing and implementing questionnaire surveys to gather input from the general public in the case study area, developing and launching university courses, and organising events with target groups.

The first questionnaire survey collected data on community, social, economic, and environmental concerns on mineral exploration and mining, among others, in Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia. From March 1st to May 15th, 2024, an online survey was conducted to gather responses from the case study residents. Of those who responded to the survey, 1068 finished and submitted their answers, 849 answered partially, and 1100 expressed interest but did not finish. This survey aims to foster sustainable mining and mineral exploration throughout the case study region, improve community involvement, and provide information for policy suggestions.

The "European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)" online university courses were introduced concurrently by the WP2 of the AGEMERA project in partnership with five higher educational institutions (HEIs) in the project. All the completed live lectures of courses from 4th March to 19th April 2024 were intended to teach students about the significance of CRMs, responsible resourcing and the value chain of CRMs. Courses targeted TUBAF, TT, OU, UL, and UNZA students but were open to any interested participants worldwide. Seventy-three students from more than 25 countries signed up for these courses. Most of them were from TUBAF, demonstrating a high level of participation from various academic backgrounds, and a countable number of participants also represented the UO, TT, and UNZA. Thirty-three of the registrants finished the online test and gave feedback on the courses, proving their commitment to the initiatives and earning themselves a certificate of attendance.

Moreover, WP2 organised seminars, workshops, and public awareness campaigns around Europe on critical metals and minerals. There were three public events with extensive attendees, two workshops, and three seminars. These events promoted open discussion among various stakeholders, including civil society representatives, industry professionals, and students. Furthermore, a communication plan has been developed to ensure continuous participation and assessment using pre- and post-event surveys that assess public awareness of forthcoming events and social acceptance.

WP2's multidimensional strategy highlights AGEMERA's dedication to enhancing sustainable practices and encouraging community involvement in the EU's critical raw materials mining and exploration sectors.

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List of Acronyms

AGEMERA	Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials
BC	Before Christ
CRMA	Critical Raw Materials Act
CRMs	Critical Raw Materials
CSRMs	Critical and Strategic Raw Materials
COA	Certificate of Attendance
CRIRSCO	Committee for Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards
DGGV	German Geological Society – Geological Association
ECRMs	European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EU	European Union
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GTK	Geological Survey of Finland
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEI	Higher Education Institution
MCs	Micro-credentials
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPAL	Online-Plattform für Akademisches Lehren und Lernen
PPGIS	Public Participation Geographic Information Systems
REEs	Rare earth elements
SLO	Social license to operate
SLE	Social license to explore
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
S-AMR	Master of Science (M. Sc.) in Advanced Mineral Resources Development
S-GEO	Diploma (Dipl.-Ing.) Geoengineering

S-MORE	Master of Science (M. Sc.) in Sustainable Mining and Remediation Management
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNRMS	United Nations Resource Management System
UNFC	United Nations Framework Classification for Resources
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WP	Work package

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) are crucial to many high-tech applications, such as advanced manufacturing, digital infrastructure, electric vehicles, and renewable energy technologies (European Commission, 2020). In addition, these resources are essential for advancing technology, accomplishing sustainability objectives, and lessening environmental impact. In response to CRMs' growing importance in speeding up the world's shift to greener, more digitally-driven economies, the EU-funded AGEMERA project, "Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials", intends to contribute to achieving sustainability on the CRMs value chain through multi-core initiatives (Islam et al., 2023).

Ensuring responsible, sustainable, and secure supply is essential in the EU. By providing a steady supply from local and foreign sources of CRMs, the EU can become less dependent on other competitive nations and gain greater strategic autonomy (European Parliament, 2023). During responsible sourcing, the social license to operate (SLO) or social license to explore (SLE) in the mining or exploration industry play a vital role in business risk. Maintaining SLE and SLO is essential to comprehending community social and cultural dynamics and local and regional environmental attitudes and concerns (Wajid et al., 2022).

To address local acceptance and sustainability of mineral exploration and mining, the AGEMERA project conducted extensive public opinion questionnaire surveys in Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia, following a similar pilot survey in Finland. These surveys investigate social sustainability issues and general attitudes towards mineral exploration and mining effects. The survey is enhanced with SoftGIS-based data and includes information relevant to each case study area, both geographically and culturally.

In addition to the questionnaire survey, the project has developed university courses called "European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition" (ECRMs), which aim to raise awareness of CRMs and their importance in everyday life among future scientists and engineers. While the courses are aimed at students in higher education institutions (HEIs), the content is available free of charge to anyone who registers on the online platform where the courses take place. These courses provide educational resources to help understand the opportunities and challenges of the CRM industry, the complex processes involved, the value chain, and the green and digital transition. The thematic focus is on specific CRMs, such as rare earth elements (REEs) and battery raw materials (BRMs), including lithium, nickel, cobalt, graphite and many more. The lectures incorporate geological and engineering information while addressing geopolitical, economic, marketing, social and environmental aspects. Additionally, it provides information on the UN Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDG) and international sustainable resource classification frameworks, including the UN

Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) and the UN Resource Management System (UNRMS).

Furthermore, the project has invested considerable effort into planning, organising, and conducting several public awareness events, seminars, and workshops on CRMs. These initiatives seek to clarify how these critical materials affect day-to-day existence, the viability of associated projects, the environment, and the processes related to mine closure. The event activities will include university students, community members, legislators, entrepreneurs, and everybody interested in this topic. Through the initiatives mentioned above, the project wants to consider different perspectives on critical raw materials.

1.2 Objectives of the Report

The report and its goals can be classified into three thematic sections:

- Give a thorough rundown of the actions to implement questionnaire surveys in the four case study regions – Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia. Case studies, communication strategy implementation, and the key figures in the collected public opinion data are all included in this section. It also contains the areas for improvement and the final survey plan.
- Discuss and evaluate the results and lessons learned from creating and executing the "European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)" university courses. This involves adding the most recent field knowledge to higher education curricula, communicating, evaluating participation in the courses, assessing participant input, and assessing the courses' benefits.
- The final objective is to highlight the workshops, seminars, and public events on critical minerals and metals that were organised, scheduled and carried out within the project. This section emphasises the main points discussed, target audiences, goals, communication strategy development, and further public awareness plans.

2 First Launch Questionnaire Implementation

2.1 Background Information

The first launch questionnaire survey aimed to obtain information on socioeconomic, environmental, and community-related concerns, among others, from the case study area of Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia. Of those who participated in the online survey, 1068 successfully finished and submitted their responses for the project, while 849 completed a portion but did not submit their responses. Furthermore, 1100 bounce visitors were initially interested in the questions but stopped before proceeding with the survey. The gathered data and information will help the project's researchers create suggestions regarding well-informed policy, improve community involvement, and advance sustainable development methods in the case study area's mineral exploration and mining sectors.

2.2 Case Study Areas

2.2.1 Estonia

The study was conducted in northeast Estonia, where the deposit area of phosphorite and graptolite argillite is located. The region includes ten municipalities and the city of Rakvere, which has a total population of 65 thousand. The town of Rakvere is the centre of an area with a growing population.

The study area is a valuable farmland with a rich historical and cultural heritage. The first signs of human habitation date back to 8700 BC. This region is historically and politically significant. In 1970, when Estonia was part of the Soviet Union, plans were started for phosphorite mining. At the time, local Estonian politicians and environmental activists saw this as an opportunity to discuss environmental problems and thereby influence local politics openly. The dangers of phosphate mining became more widely known in Estonia in the 1980s, culminating in protests against the then government.

Demand for raw materials and technological development are giving new value to the mineral resources in the study area (phosphorite and graptolite argillite). Today, the Estonian Geological Service is conducting new phosphorite surveys there due to the European mineral policy. In addition to strategic raw materials, the region has construction materials and working limestone quarries. Near the study area on the eastern side is the Estonian oil shale industry, which has provided employment and influenced the entire Ida-Viru County for over a century, and currently, the transformation of the oil shale industry is transforming into the chemical industry. The region's inhabitants have been affected by large-scale sectors for a long time, and the manifestations of this environmental impact also shape the current understanding of mineral resource extraction in a large area.

Figure 1 shows the map of the research area for phosphorite and graptolite argillite, the centre of which is the city of Rakvere. The east of the study area is the oil shale industry with its mines and quarries, and the west is primarily sandy gravel and forested and

marshy areas. The study area is forested, with agricultural lands and smaller quarries of construction minerals (sand, gravel, limestone).

Figure 1. Estonian phosphorite and graptolite argillite study area in Virumaa

2.2.2 Germany

The German region of Saxony's Erzgebirge, also known as the Ore Mountains, was the pivotal case study site in Germany for the first launch of the questionnaire public survey. Nestled in the southern region of the Free State of Saxony, the Erzgebirge stands as the most densely populated upland area in Europe. Its strategic connection to the Autobahn system through the A4 and A72 and its proximity to the major Saxon cities make it a significant hub of economic activity.

The Erzgebirge region, a UNESCO World Heritage site, offers a unique perspective within the German environment. Renowned for its rich cultural legacy and historical mining significance, the area is a testament to 800 years of continuous mining activity. Its attractive scenery, peaceful towns, and solid regional heritage and identity make it a fascinating case study area. Notable features include smelting sites, mining cities, new mineral processing techniques, and inventive water management (UNESCO, 2019).

The UNESCO World Heritage site Erzgebirge/Krušnohoří mining region is a complex of 22 components, 17 of which are in Germany (Figure 2) and situated in the case study area. Figure 2 shows the map of the 17 Erzgebirge mining region world heritage site components, each with a number of extra items denoting the region's outstanding universal value and historical mining heritage. This historic cultural environment, shaped by 800 years of continuous mining activity, is a testament to the region's rich mining heritage and enduring cultural impact.

Figure 2. The 17 components of the Erzgebirge Mining Region World Heritage Site (modified after Wirtschaftsförderung Erzgebirge GmbH, 2019)

2.2.3 Poland

In Poland, the case study for the first launch of the questionnaire public survey was conducted in the Lower Silesia region, focusing on the LGOM area (Figure 3). This area is situated in the southwest part of Poland, close to Legnica and Lubin. This region is easily accessed through a different communication system such as car transport through Highway A4 and Expressway S3, railways and the international airport in Wrocław. This area is also near the border with Germany and the Czech Republic. For centuries, this region has been connected with a strong mining industry, both open pits and underground. Mining activity in this region started 800 years ago. Minerals, silver, and gold were exploited, among others. In the last 50 years, the most active mining has been connected with copper, which has been exploited since the 60's last century. Apart from active mines, there are also many historic places like Złoty Stok old gold mine and Centre of Science and Art Old Mine in Wałbrzych. Locations of different kinds of mineral resources are shown in Figure 3. Nowadays, the most significant mining activity is located near Lubin city, where KGHM Polska Miedź, one of the largest copper produced in the world, owns three deep copper mines.

Figure 3. Location of different mineral resources in the Lower Silesia region (Solecki et al., 2017)

2.2.4 Zambia

The partner UNZA used the North-Western Province of Zambia as the case study area in the questionnaire survey (Figure 4). As of 2021, it had 1,278,357 residents, with a population density of 20 people per square kilometre over 125,826 km². This province has the lowest population density in the country.

The primary economic activity of North Western province is mining. There are two active mines in the province: Kansanshi, Lumwana, and Kalumbila, both located in the Solwezi district of the province. In the largely rural area, social activity has increased due to the recent mining of ore deposits in the North Western Province. Manyama, a nearby community of the mines, has seen major changes due to the influx of migrants from other regions of the country who have come to work in those mines.

Figure 4. The case study area of Zambia - North-Western Province is highlighted with red colour

2.3 Questionnaire and Privacy Policy Formulation

2.3.1 Questionnaire Formulation

In the pilot case study in Finland, the developed questionnaire related to the social sustainability and acceptance of mineral exploration and mining was implemented and assessed during the first year of the project duration. The pilot questionnaire structure and initiative accomplished the project's objective of gathering viewpoints and insights from the pilot case study area. In addition, the questionnaire has acknowledged the possibility of broader use. Considering the pilot survey's success, the pilot questionnaire has consequently been modified and employed in countries such as Germany, Estonia, Poland, and Zambia by the partners involved in the initiatives.

Each local project partner made targeted adjustments to reflect country-specific unique features to ensure the questionnaire's relevance and accuracy across various locations. These adjustments included localised case study area municipalities, names of renowned mining and mineral exploration companies in the area, and adjusting the

questions to correspond with the varied educational systems of every country. In addition, the critical raw materials potential maps from each case study of each country were added to the collection map-based responses. As the original questionnaire was developed in English, another step of each case study partner was to convert the questionnaire into local languages and upload the questionnaire to the common web-based platform.

2.3.2 Privacy Policy

One of the most important initiatives in preparing for the first questionnaire survey across multiple nations was creating a privacy policy for each case study partner. Ensuring participants were informed, approved to use responded data, and aware of their rights under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), consent to this policy was essential for ethical and legal compliance.

Each partner received a common privacy policy template for customisation with the local regulations and legislation. This template included details about the types of questions, the scope of the survey, and data usage, an assurance of independent choice with the option to discontinue at any moment, explanations regarding possible risks and advantages for participants and the community, confidentiality safeguards such as secure storage and data anonymisation, and the contact information of the involved researchers and ethical local members.

2.3.2.1 Template of the privacy consent provided to each case study partner for the adjustment

Data Protection Regulation for 'name of the case study area'

Date: DD/MM/YY

i. Information for research participants, respondents of the questionnaire

'Full name of the partner organisation' studies local people's views on the mineral industry (mineral exploration and mining) as part of the AGEMERA project funded by the European Commission (Grant Agreement 101058178). The research areas are 'case study names of the partner.'

This privacy notice emphasises that participation in the questionnaire survey is entirely voluntary. There will be no negative consequences for anyone if they choose not to participate in the research or decide to withdraw at any time. However, if someone withdraws from the study, the data collected before the withdrawal can still be used in the research. For more information regarding your rights and how you can affect the processing of your personal data, please see the end of this notice.

ii. Data controller

Add 'Partner organisation name', 'address' and contact persons from the responsible local/case study-related partners who can respond to questions and provide other relevant contact information within the organisation and project.

iii. Description of the research project and purpose of personal data processing

The data will be collected through a web-based questionnaire platform. The survey is designed to gather unique and valuable perceptions of mineral exploration and mining from the local respondents. It includes questions about the acceptance of ore exploration and mining, the effects of ore exploration and the distribution of benefits and harms, the possibility of participating and influencing decision-making, and compensation for potential harms caused by materials exploration and extraction. The personal data that will be collected includes [specific types of personal data, e.g., age, gender, occupation]. Your response or input is not just important; it's crucial for achieving the research project objectives, and we highly value your participation.

The survey also includes more general questions about environmental problems and concerns and trust in various actors in issues related to the extractive industry. In addition, the respondents are asked to write about their views on the future of their residence, their relationship with it, possible intentions to move, and the reasons affecting them.

The survey also contains map questions, where the respondents can mark on the map the areas for which they think the extractive industry's activities are suitable and the regions in which they would like to remain untouched. In addition, the survey collects background information about the respondents, such as age, education, industry, municipality of residence, and current postal/zip code.

The information is only used for research purposes and is not disclosed to actors outside the AGEMERA project. The data is also anonymised, so it is impossible to identify individual respondents.

iv. Parties and division of responsibilities of the research collaboration

The University of Lapland and the project coordinator, the University of Oulu in Finland, designed the survey. As many AGEMERA project partners as possible should test it in different national contexts. The goal is to develop a survey tool (based on the comparison) that can also be used after the project. The original data is used only by the 'name of the partner organisation'.

v. The researcher responsible for the case study responsible for the further study

Add here the name of the researcher responsible for the questionnaire and the address, phone number, and email address.

vi. Contact information of the data protection officer

Previously, inform the lawyer, legal advisor, and legal office from the local partner organisation about the questionnaire approach and privacy notice. Add the name and contact information of the legal person and a responsible member from the local project partner here.

vii. Name, type, and duration of the questionnaire survey

Name: Local people's perceptions of mineral exploration and mining in 'organisation name of the partner'.

Type: Quantitative research (questionnaire).

Duration: The questionnaire will be open from March 1st to May 15th, 2024. After that, the survey may be repeated before the end of the AGEMERA project (31.7.2025), a follow-up study. The material can be used in scientific articles, research reports, and theses during or after the project duration.

viii. Legal basis for personal data processing

Performance of a task carried out in exercising official authority vested in the controller: scientific research.

ix. Level of personal data collection and processing in the questionnaire survey

The questionnaire survey and research do not collect or discuss information about the respondents on an individual level. Background questions include the year of birth, gender, level of education, industry, municipality of residence, zip code of the apartment, length of time living in the municipality in years and the respondent's estimate of how long he/she thinks he/she will still live there. The themes of the other questions are described in the section 'Description of the research project and purpose of personal data processing'.

The survey collects both numerical and written information. Numerical data consists of answers given by respondents to question matrices and multiple-choice questions, and written data includes answers to open questions.

x. Sensitive personal data

The survey does not ask for sensitive personal information (e.g., Racial or ethnic origins, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, genetic data, biometric data to uniquely identify a natural person, health, or sexual orientation).

xi. Sources of personal data

All information is collected from the respondents themselves, and providing information is voluntary for the respondents.

xii. Data transfer or disclosure outside the research group

The survey material will not be handed over to anyone.

xiii. Data transfer or disclosure outside the EU or the European Economic Area

Questionnaire data is not transferred or disclosed outside the EU or the European Economic Area except UNZA-owned data from Zambia.

xiv. Automated decisions

No automated decisions are made.

xv. Safeguards to protect personal data

The collected data is confidential. The pseudonymised survey data will be stored on password—and username-protected computers and, if necessary, on backup encrypted hard drives and/or memory sticks. When data is exchanged between the researcher(s), for example, due to co-authorship or other reasons, it will always be anonymised. Direct identifiers are not collected during the questionnaire survey.

xvi. Processing of personal data after the end of the study

The questionnaire survey initiative ends on 31.7.2025, and at the same time, the AGEMERA project ends. After that, the data will be saved for five years, and if the follow-up studies continue, the safeguarded data will be saved for five years after the study.

xvii. What rights do you have, and deviation from rights

The contact person in matters related to the subject's rights is mentioned in the Data Controller section of this notice.

xviii. Right to lodge a complaint.

Anyone can file a complaint with the data protection commissioner's office/authority in their country if they believe that valid data protection legislation has been violated in processing their personal data. Add the authority and address to which the complaint should be sent.

This privacy notice is archived in the 'name of the partner organisation'.

2.4 Communication Strategies in Case Study Areas

2.4.1 Estonia

In Estonia, a communication plan was created to inform about the survey. The information activity started with a press release in public media about conducting the study. Callisto, the communication partner of the Institute of Geology of Tallinn University of Technology, with which the institute has a long-term cooperation, created the press release. The plan included the creation of the press release and, if necessary, follow-up communication activities and communication with the press. The press release was successful and published in various online news channels (Figures 5 and 6).

Figure 5. Screenshot of the research survey news on Estonia's innovation online news page

Figure 6. Screenshot of the research survey news on Estonia's largest green technology online news page

As a result, an interview was given to news radio KUKU regarding critical commodities and Estonia's options. Some local municipalities and cities also added this news to their website (Figure 7-9).

Figure 7. Screenshot of the news of the research survey on the page of the municipality of Vinni

The news was successful, but it did not lead to the expected large number of responses, so a more personal approach was chosen for the next activity in direct relationship with the municipalities. E-mails were sent to the municipalities' general contact addresses. Some municipalities also asked for more explanatory text about the study, which they would then display on their website.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the news of the research survey on the page of the municipality of Lügänuše

Figure 9. Screenshot of the news of the research survey on the page of the city of Rakvere

2.4.2 Germany

The first launch questionnaire survey was communicated in the Erzgebirge region of Saxony, Germany, following several steps and methods. First, a short survey description and the survey link were added to the webpage of the TU Bergakademie Freiberg under the project description (Figure 10). In the second stage, a press release was conducted to attract the local media and press and reach the information to the relevant organisations in the area (Figure 11).

As a result, several local media outlets and organisations were attracted by the survey information. For example, Radio Erzgebirge, a prominent local media outlet in the area, has published the survey information on its website (Figure 12). Relevant organisations such as the German Geological Society (DGGV) have also published the survey information on their website (Figure 13). However, after all the efforts, the number of responses was unsatisfactory.

Then, it was decided to keep the survey information up-to-date throughout the survey (1 March to 15 May 2024) through continuous posts on the TU Bergakademie Freiberg's social media pages (Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, etc.), continuously informing the local press and media. For example, the end day of the week was chosen to post the survey information on social media to allow the public to use their weekend to provide their opinions. The social media efforts attracted the area's users, resulted in several reposts, and increased the number of responses. In addition, an extended duration of the survey helped get more responses.

Online-Umfrage

Im Rahmen des von der Europäischen Kommission geförderten Forschungsprojektes AGEMERA (Grant Agreement ID: 101058178) wird in den kommenden Wochen eine online-basierte Befragung zur Meinung der lokalen Bevölkerung hinsichtlich der Exploration und Gewinnung mineralischer Rohstoffe durchgeführt. Diese Umfrage erfolgt mit Hilfe eines Online-Fragebogens, der im Rahmen des Projektes in Finnland entwickelt und getestet wurde und in einem zweiten Schritt jetzt in Deutschland und weiteren Partnerländern (Estland, Polen und Sambia) ab dem 1. März bis zum 15. Mai 2024 öffentlich zugänglich ist. Lokaler Partner im AGEMERA-Projekt ist das Institut für Bergbau und Spezialtiefbau der TUBAF.

Mit dieser Umfrage wird unter anderem die Akzeptanz der lokalen Bevölkerung gegenüber der Exploration und Gewinnung mineralischer Rohstoffe erfragt und die damit verbundenen Vor- und Nachteile für die lokale Wirtschaft, für das gesellschaftliche Zusammenleben in der Region und für die Umwelt. Darüber hinaus werden die Befragten gebeten, ihre Meinung zu wichtigen Wirtschaftszweigen und der Zukunft ihres Wohnortes, ihre Beziehung zum Wohnort sowie mögliche Abwanderungsabsichten und deren Einflussfaktoren zu äußern.

Ebenso sind Fragen bezüglich des Vertrauens in verschiedene Akteure der Rohstoffindustrie enthalten. Kartenbasierte Elemente der Online-Umfrage ermöglichen es den Teilnehmern, Gebiete auf einer Karte als geeignet oder ungeeignet für Aktivitäten der Rohstoffindustrie zu markieren. Die Befragung erfasst sowohl numerische als auch schriftliche Informationen. Die numerischen Daten inkludieren die Antworten auf Fragematrizen und Multiple-Choice-Fragen, während die schriftlichen Daten die Antworten auf offene Fragen umfassen. Es werden keine personenbezogenen Daten erhoben. Die Teilnehmer werden daher ausdrücklich gebeten, in ihren Antworten keine personenbezogenen Daten anzugeben. Es ist geplant, die Befragung vor dem Ende des AGEMERA-Projekts (31. Juli 2025) in Form einer Folgestudie zu wiederholen.

Ihre freiwillige Teilnahme an der Umfrage ist entscheidend, um ein umfassendes Verständnis für die Nachhaltigkeitsparameter in Bezug auf die Exploration und Gewinnung mineralischer Rohstoffe im Erzgebirge zu entwickeln.

Wenn Sie Fragen zum Projekt und zur Umfrage an der TU Bergakademie Freiberg haben, wenden Sie sich bitte per E-Mail an Herrn Ariful Islam (md-ariful.islam@mabb.tu-freiberg.de) oder Herrn Georg Meißner (georg.meissner@mabb.tu-freiberg.de). Für Rückfragen zu den Inhalten steht weiterhin Frau Leena Suopajarvi als Urheberin des Fragebogens wie folgt zur Verfügung:

Frau Leena Suopajarvi
leena.suopajarvi@lapland.fi
 University of Lapland
 Postbox 122, 96101 Rovaniemi (Finland).

Seite teilen:

[f](#) [X](#) [v](#) [in](#) [e](#) [p](#)

Figure 10. Screenshot of the survey description on the website of the TU Bergakademie Freiberg

Online-Befragung verlängert bis 30. April: Exploration und Gewinnung mineralischer Rohstoffe im Erzgebirge

Startseite / News

Im Rahmen des EU-Forschungsprojektes AGEMERA wird in den kommenden Wochen eine Online-Umfrage zu den Ansichten der lokalen Bevölkerung hinsichtlich der Exploration und Gewinnung mineralischer Rohstoffe im Erzgebirge durchgeführt. Der Fragebogen wurde im Rahmen des Projekts in Finnland entwickelt und getestet und wird nun auch in Deutschland und weiteren Partnerländern des Forschungsprojekts angewendet. Die Umfrage ist noch bis zum 30. April 2024 öffentlich zugänglich. Lokaler Partner im AGEMERA-Projekt ist die Professur für Rohstoffabbau und Spezialverfahren unter Tage der TU Bergakademie Freiberg.

24. April 2024

Forschung

Seite teilen:

[f](#) [X](#) [v](#) [in](#) [e](#) [p](#)

Die Forschenden fragen vornehmlich die Akzeptanz der lokalen Bevölkerung von Explorations- und Rohstoffprojekten ab. Außerdem beschäftigt sich die Umfrage mit den damit assoziierten Vor- und Nachteile für die lokale Wirtschaft, für das gesellschaftliche Zusammenleben in der Region und für die Umwelt. Enthalten sind auch Fragen bezüglich des Vertrauens in verschiedene Akteure der Rohstoffindustrie.

Zur [Online-Umfrage](#) und weiteren [Projektinformationen](#).

Eine möglichst breite Teilnahme an der Umfrage ist entscheidend, um ein umfassendes Verständnis für Nachhaltigkeitsparameter in Bezug auf die Exploration und Gewinnung mineralischer Rohstoffe im Erzgebirge zu entwickeln. Es werden keine personenbezogenen Daten erhoben. Es ist geplant, die Befragung vor dem Ende des AGEMERA-Projekts (31. Juli 2025) in Form einer Folgestudie zu wiederholen.

Weiterführende Fragen zur Umfrage beantwortet agemera@tu-freiberg.de

Figure 11. Screenshot of the press release to attract the local media and press

Umfrage zu Rohstoffgewinnung

Zuletzt aktualisiert: 06.03.2024 | 20:47 Uhr Autor: [Sindy Einhorn](#)

 LINK

Im Rahmen eines EU-Forschungsprojektes läuft gerade eine Online-Umfrage, und zwar geht es darum, wie die Leute zur Gewinnung von Rohstoffen hier im Erzgebirge stehen. Darüber hat die TU Freiberg jetzt informiert.

Die Forscher fragen vor allem ab, ob Projekte zur Rohstoffgewinnung bei der Bevölkerung vor Ort akzeptiert werden. Die Umfrage beschäftigt sich auch damit, welche Vor- und Nachteile für die lokale Wirtschaft angenommen werden und für die Umwelt. Enthalten sind außerdem Fragen zum Vertrauen in verschiedene Akteure der Rohstoffindustrie.

Noch bis 1. April kann jeder mitmachen. Die Projektinformationen und die Online-Umfrage sind auf der Website der TU Bergakademie Freiberg zu finden. Zur Umfrage geht es [hier](#).

Figure 12. Screenshot of the survey information on the website of Radio Erzgebirge

[Mitgliedschaft](#)
[GeoShop](#)
[Spenden](#)
[Forum](#)

[Publikationen](#)
[Geologie erleben](#)
[Bildungsangebote](#)
[Fachsektionen & Arbeitskreise](#)
[Aktuelles](#)
[Über uns](#)

E-Publikationen
Zeitschriften der DGGV

Exploration und Gewinnung mineralischer Rohstoffe im Erzgebirge.

Im Rahmen des EU-Forschungsprojektes AGEMERA wird in den kommenden Wochen eine Online-Umfrage zu den Ansichten der lokalen Bevölkerung hinsichtlich der Exploration und Gewinnung mineralischer Rohstoffe im Erzgebirge durchgeführt. Der Fragebogen wurde im Rahmen des Projekts in Finnland entwickelt und getestet und wird nun auch in Deutschland und weiteren Partnerländern des Forschungsprojekts angewendet. Die Umfrage ist noch bis zum 30. April 2024 öffentlich zugänglich. Lokaler Partner im AGEMERA-Projekt ist die Professur für Rohstoffabbau und Spezialverfahren unter Tage der TU Bergakademie Freiberg.

Die Forschenden fragen vornehmlich die Akzeptanz der lokalen Bevölkerung von Explorations- und Rohstoffprojekten ab. Außerdem beschäftigt sich die Umfrage mit den damit assoziierten Vor- und Nachteile für die lokale Wirtschaft, für das gesellschaftliche Zusammenleben in der Region und für die Umwelt. Enthalten sind auch Fragen bezüglich des Vertrauens in verschiedene Akteure der Rohstoffindustrie.

Zur [Online-Umfrage](#) und weiteren [Projektinformationen](#).

Eine möglichst breite Teilnahme an der Umfrage ist entscheidend, um ein umfassendes Verständnis für Nachhaltigkeitsparameter in Bezug auf die Exploration und Gewinnung mineralischer Rohstoffe im Erzgebirge zu entwickeln. Es werden keine personenbezogenen Daten erhoben. Es ist geplant, die Befragung vor dem Ende des AGEMERA-Projekts (31. Juli 2025) in Form einer Folgestudie zu wiederholen.

Weiterführende Fragen zur Umfrage beantwortet agemera@tu-freiberg.de

Figure 13. Screenshot of the survey information on the website of the German Geological Society (DGGV)

2.4.3 Poland

To collect appropriate feedback, the questionnaire was sent to the community living in the Lower Silesian region, where the only currently exploited copper deposit in Poland is located. This area is also an area of high-risk exploration activities, so feedback from the local community may be valuable from the point of view of this survey.

Information about the survey was disseminated on KGHM CUPRUM social media (Facebook, LinkedIn). Thanks to cooperation with the Wrocław University of Science and Technology, the survey was also sent to students living in the Lower Silesian region. Additionally, information about the AGEMERA project and the survey was placed on the intranet of the KGHM capital group, to which over 30,000 people have access.

Responses were closely tracked throughout the communication to ensure the intended objectives were fulfilled. When combined with the careful execution of all associated responsibilities, these communication efforts gathered more than 60 submitted responses.

2.4.4 Zambia

WhatsApp is a key tool for connecting people in Zambia, both in urban and rural areas, through communication. Due to its accessibility and popularity, UNZA deliberately chose WhatsApp to distribute the questionnaire survey in the case study area. A set of focused messages was developed to ensure wide coverage and involvement with the questionnaire survey efforts. Each message was modified to speak to particular demographics and interest groups within the case study to ensure relevance and elicit meaningful replies.

The outcomes were quite promising. Enthusiastic respondents spontaneously amplified the survey's outcome by disseminating the information to their networks. The interactive and dynamic survey process allowed participants to ask questions, get clarifications, and instantaneously share their ideas. This two-way communication channel improved the data gathered and promoted a feeling of ownership and responsibility in the community. In conclusion, considering the population density of the Zambian case study, UNZA's choice to use WhatsApp as the questionnaire survey's medium effectively attracted a sizable audience.

2.5 Main Figures of the Questionnaire Survey

2.5.1 Overall Overview of the Survey

On the landing page of the first-launch questionnaire survey, respondents could choose their preferred language (Figure 14), follow brief instructions to complete the questions and consent to the privacy policy. Before participants answered the questions, it was mentioned that only the submitted responses at the end would be counted.

Figure 14. The landing page of the first launch questionnaire survey

The questionnaire implementation was completed with 1068 submitted respondents, 849 unsubmitted respondents, and 1100 bounce visitors. However, the questions' specific submitted response numbers differ from the total submitted responses shown in Table 1. Furthermore, question-specific responses are higher for several questions than submitted responses.

Table 1. The number of responses achieved for specific questions and the number of submitted responses

Themes of the Questions	Total	Submitted	Percentage (%) of Submission
Birth year	1351	753	55.73
Gender	1882	1024	54.41
Level of education	1830	1004	54.86
Socio-economic status	1820	1008	55.38
Working sector	1380	782	56.67
Informed about mineral exploration	1776	1016	57.21
Personal contact with companies	513	368	71.73
Benefits and harms	1498	1010	67.42
Effects of mineral exploration on other business	1057	753	71.24
Future of your home region	1397	1002	71.72
Least important economic sector	929	681	73.30
Biggest threats for 2050	1071	825	77.03
Mineral exploration's social impacts	1306	1005	76.95
Concerned about the effect of mineral exploration	1018	782	76.82
Local people's participation and influence	1263	1001	79.25
Compensation for the harms	776	624	80.41
Environmental concern	1014	820	80.87
Mineral exploration's effects on the environment	943	766	81.23
Environmental problems associated with mining affect views on mineral exploration	895	730	81.56
Source of reliable information about the extractive sector	657	549	83.56
Primary municipality of residence	926	779	84.12
Home postal code	759	648	85.37
Relationship with the area	914	779	85.22
Region Selection	802	686	85.53
How to find the survey	969	962	99.27

Around 54-57% of respondents answer questions about their socioeconomic status, gender, year of birth, and degree of education. This suggests that the completion rates for demographic and personal questions were comparatively lower. However, the submission rates for questions concerning the primary municipality of residence, the home postal code, the association with the area, and the method of accessing the survey

are very high, frequently exceeding 85%. Nearly all respondents finished the "How to find the survey" section, as evidenced by the high rate of 99.27%. This is probably because it was simple to complete and needed little work.

The submission rates for awareness and perception-related questions, such as knowing the effects of mining exploration, range from 67% to 77%. In general, more careful answers are needed to these queries. Conversely, inquiries concerning environmental issues, social consequences, and community involvement demonstrate greater response rates, typically surpassing 80%. This implies that questions about environmental and community concerns aroused respondents' interest more.

Figure 15. Year of birth distribution of the respondents

The survey's respondents were divided into different birth year groups, and their distributions varied (Figure 15). With roughly 34.2% of respondents, the largest section of respondents group was those born between 1965 and 1980. Approximately 32.8% of respondents were born between 1981 and 1996 and came in second place. Furthermore, the respondents born between 1946 and 1964 accounted for about 29.5%. Finally, in the birth years between 1997 and 2012, the youngest group represented roughly 21.2% of the respondents.

In total, 1,882 respondents provided gender information (Figure 16). Male respondents comprised over 52% of the total, with female respondents comprising about 46%. Just 2% of respondents said they were unsure of their gender. With a small male predominance, the gender distribution shows a fairly equal involvement from male and female respondents.

Figure 16. Gender distribution of questionnaire survey respondents

In total, 1,830 respondents disclosed their educational backgrounds (Figure 17). With over half (50.76%) of the total responses, respondents with a higher education background comprise the largest category. Respondents with a college degree or specialised vocational training comprise 25.02%, while upper secondary education comes third at 18.90%. With 0.71% and 1.15% of all replies, those enrolled in comprehensive and primary schools are underrepresented.

One thousand eight hundred twenty respondents disclosed their socioeconomic position (Figure 18). A diverse representation is evident in the distribution of respondents across various categories: 16.09% identified as students, while 55.76% reported being employed. Retired respondents were 14.95%, while the remaining groups were 2.86% unemployed, 2.47% stay-at-home or family caregivers, 0.93% in the armed forces or other national services, and 6.97% other. This breakdown highlights most working adults and students, who comprise more than 72.85% of all responders. In conclusion, the survey data could shed light on the various viewpoints and experiences held by people in various occupational positions and their contribution to understanding the various themes of the questionnaire survey.

Figure 17. Education-level of the respondents

Figure 18. Socio-economic status of the respondents

To see the overall view, 55.71% of respondents to the first launch questionnaire survey eventually submitted their answers, according to the total number of recorded responses. Although 44.29% of responses contain numerous completed questions, the respondents did not submit their responses to be included in the project's research evaluation by the end. This large percentage of incomplete responses draws attention to potential issues with the survey process and further improvement scope in the final survey initiative. The respondent's submitted answers will be considered for evaluation.

2.5.2 Estonia

The summary from Estonia's initial launch questionnaire survey is shown in Table 2. The respondents' gender distribution reveals an almost equal distribution between males (48.2%) and females (48.0%), with a minor percentage (3.8%) identifying as "Other." About 33.0% of respondents answered that they live in TT's selected case study areas, while 33.4% described that they are from other parts of Estonia than the case study area. The socioeconomic situation of the respondents varied greatly, with 58.4% reported being employed, while 18.1% were pensioners, and without employment (3.8%) were the next largest group. Students comprise 1.3% of the total, and the remaining 15% of respondents fall into other categories.

Table 2. Main figures of the first launch questionnaire survey in Estonia

		Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	329	48.0
	Male	330	48.2
	Other	26	3.8
Respondent's Residence	Case Study Area	226	33.0
	Other Area	229	33.4
	Not Mentioned	230	33.6
Socioeconomic status	Employed	400	58.4
	Student	9	1.3
	Unemployed	26	3.8
	Retired	124	18.1
	Other	103	15.0
	Not Mentioned	23	3.4

2.5.3 Germany

The Free State Saxony, with a concentration on the Erzgebirge region in the east of Germany, was the communication focus of the first questionnaire survey conducted in Germany by the AGEMERA project. After checking fully and partially answered submissions, 174 responses were found. Table 3 summarises the main features of the gathered survey data from the region.

Of the 174 respondents, 97 respondents (55.74%) did not provide any information about their primary residence, and just 77 respondents (44.25%) provided information about their principal municipality of residence. Of the 77 respondents who provided information about their places of residence, 87% reside primarily in the Free State of Saxony, and 61% have primary residence in the Erzgebirge region of Germany.

Furthermore, the percentage of male respondents (60.34%) is about twice that of female respondents (33.90%). Regarding the respondents' socioeconomic level, 7.47% identify as students, 8.62% as retirees, and 70.11% as employed. Comparing the responses of unemployed respondents to the state's average unemployment rate (5.6%, Federal Republic of Germany 2022), the representation of unemployed people is deficient (0.57%) among the respondents.

Table 3. Main figures of the first launch questionnaire survey in Germany

		Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	59	33.90
	Male	105	60.34
	Not Mentioned	10	5.74
Respondent's Residence	Residence Information	77	44.25
	No Information	97	55.74
	Erzgebirge Region	47	61.03*
	Free State of Saxony	67**	87.01*
	Other	10	12.99*
Socioeconomic status	Employed	122	70.11
	Student	13	7.47
	Unemployed	1	0.57
	Retired	15	8.62
	Other	13	7.47
	Not Mentioned	10	5.75

* Values are among the number of residence information; ** Value also includes the number for Erzgebirge region

2.5.4 Poland

There is a noticeable difference between the number of submitted responses and those not from the first launch questionnaire survey in the Lower Silesian region of Poland. Of the 100 responses from Poland, 62 respondents submitted their answers at the end, which will be considered for additional analysis in the project's research study by the CUP and KGHM partner.

A few key points of the total respondents from Poland have been summarised in Table 4. Table 4 reveals a wide range of respondents, with 36% identifying as female, 63% as male, and 1% as other. Respondents from the case study area comprised 46%. In comparison, almost a similar percentage (45%) did not give information regarding their place of residence, and 9% of the respondents were from outside the case study area. Eighty-six percent of the respondents were employed, representing the largest socioeconomic group. The remaining twelve percent were students, and one percent were retirees. Significantly, 1% of respondents did not disclose their status, and none were classified as unemployed or in any other socioeconomic group.

Table 4. Main figures of the first launch questionnaire survey in Poland

		Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	36	36%
	Male	63	63%
	Other	1	1%
Respondent's Residence	Case Study Area	46	46%
	Other Area	9	9%
	Not Mentioned	45	45%
Socioeconomic status	Employed	86	86%
	Student	12	12%
	Unemployed	0	0%
	Retired	1	1%
	Other	0	0%
	Not Mentioned	1	1%

2.6 Map-Based Responses and PPGIS Experiences

Public Participation GIS (PPGIS) was incorporated into the map-based survey questions as part of the project's questionnaire approach. PPGIS combines geographic information systems (GIS) and forefront information and communication technology to facilitate co-creation and interaction with the survey participants. It allowed the questionnaire survey respondents to map important sites or regions that should remain unaffected or appropriate for usage by the extractive industry. In addition, respondents had the opportunity to describe the reason or their thoughts behind the selected particular place suitable for mining and the place to be kept untouched.

By facilitating GIS and enhancing planning through multiple kinds of local insights, the PPGIS approach has turned local people into local experts and allowed the project's case study researchers to identify the location and area-specific local concerns. To make it easier for the responders, mineral potential maps were pre-added or marked on the map for each case study area in the questionnaire survey (Figures 19 & 20).

Figure 19. Mineral potential area with turquoise colour in the case study sites of Germany and Poland

Figure 20. Mineral potential area with turquoise colour in the case study site of Estonia

2.6.1 General Overview of the Responded Data

At the start of the interactive map-based questions, respondents were asked to choose their region, which automatically took them to a comprehensive regional map. After choosing their home or region of interest, the respondents were directed to that region in the map service. Within the regional data, the geology-based mineral potential was shown to help the respondents see the connection between mineral potential and possible mineral exploration targets. The respondents could map important areas and describe the reasons or thoughts behind the selected place.

The first launch questionnaire survey covered four countries, and 750 respondents selected regions from Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia (Figure 21). In addition, 52 respondents are from the Rovaniemi and Kuusamo, the pilot case study area of the questionnaire survey initiative conducted in the first year of the project in Finland. However, in the end, 686 respondents submitted their responses regarding region selection for use and count.

Figure 21. Number of region selections from different case studies

Two hundred thirteen participants responded to inquiries concerning the suitability of particular locations for using the extractive industry. They gave their views, showing an overwhelming conviction and a readiness to explain their thinking. Regarding the questions concerning more general areas appropriate for the extractive activity, 128 responses explained their choice of the selections (Table 5).

In contrast, more people answered when asked to name locations that should remain untouched. The 260 respondents who gave justifications for their decisions demonstrated significant public support for conservation and shielding specific places from extractive industries (Table 5). In response to questions about general areas, 167

respondents explained their decisions. This also demonstrated broad agreement on how crucial it is to protect some areas from the influence of the extractive industry.

Table 5. Number of explanations regarding suitable and off-limit for extractive sectors

		Total Number of Explanations	Submitted Number of Explanation	Percentage of Submission
Suitable for Extractive Sector	Locations/Points	213	202	94.84
	Areas	128	126	98.43
Should be Left Untouched	Locations/Points	260	245	94.23
	Areas	167	164	98.20

There was extensive participation in providing justifications in both categories—Suitable for the Extractive Sector and Should be Left Untouched—with submission percentages continuously surpassing 94%. This demonstrates active involvement and shows the respondents diligently give detailed information for narrowly focused locations and more general areas.

2.6.2 Distribution of Locations and Areas

Figure 22 illustrates the general spatial distribution of respondents' responses from different study regions. Respondents were related to study regions in three stages: i) the home municipality provided by the respondent was connected to the country with a jointly created "Municipality-Country" Excel file, ii) a map response area was applied if the municipality was unavailable, and iii) if the municipality and map response area were not available, response language was used as a criterion. Thus, if the given home municipality was unrelated to the study region and other responses provided unclear outcomes, this response was not included in country-specific information.

2.6.3 Distribution of Map-based Data to Case Study Partners

The University of Oulu distributed two shapefiles containing each case study's map responses (one for points and another for areas) to only the responsible partner of the case study. The two shapefiles, including map responses by points and areas, can be connected to the main questionnaire responses by "responded" in the map file and Respondent ID in the shape file. Respondents may have several map responses, which is good to consider when creating table joins/relations.

In maps files, a column "layer" holds information about the response related to Places_to_be_left_untouched—Points or Suitable_locations_for_extractive_sector—Points as well as Areas_to_be_left_untouched—Polygons or Suitable_areas_for_extractive_sector—Polygons.

Figure 22. General spatial distribution of respondents' responses from the case study area of Estonia, Germany, Poland and Zambia

2.7 Other Findings and Improvement Scope

2.7.1 Other Findings

In response to questions regarding how they noticed the survey information, 969 respondents and 962 submitting respondents provided answers (Figure 23). The majority of 543 respondents said they discovered it via social media, which demonstrates how social media platforms are useful for reaching many people. A lower portion of 78 respondents found the survey through their local newspaper, indicating that traditional media is still relevant even in a less significant way.

Figure 23 Communication and outreach status of the questionnaire survey

Friends and family also significantly promoted the survey, with 188 participants learning about it from their close acquaintances. This underscores the importance of personal recommendations in influencing survey participation. Furthermore, 160 respondents selected 'Other,' but when the responses from this section are examined, it reveals that 184 respondents submitted their answers. This suggests that case study-specific internal investigations could reveal other effective communication options.

Moreover, 253 respondents provided feedback on the survey or raised at least one topic that wasn't covered in the initial questionnaire. This input could be instrumental in identifying areas that could be improved or issues not covered in the project's final survey initiative, underscoring the value of respondent input.

2.7.2 Improvement Scope

Research teams from the UL, UO, TUBAF, TT, CUP, and UNZA are responsible for implementing several strategies into practice to increase the percentage of submitted responses in the final surveys. These may involve making the survey faster by simplifying the questions, giving more precise guidelines to the audiences, or expanding the survey's outreach through focused distribution methods. The survey questions should

be more transparent and straightforward, especially the ones that ask for demographic data and have lower submission rates. It is also important to comprehend the reasons for the 849 unsubmitted responses. These can be due to technological problems, a lack of time, or trouble comprehending the questionnaire. By addressing these problems, the survey procedure will be improved to have a greater completion rate. The research team would look into and fix any technological issues that may have led survey respondents to drop out. The team will examine the communication tactics and why the 1100 bounce visitors decided not to proceed with the questionnaire survey. Modifying the introduction, making the first questions more interesting, and lowering the perceived effort required to begin the study can turn early interest into completed responses.

2.8 Final Questionnaire Survey Plan

2.8.1 Case Study Areas and Key Responsibilities

Responsible organisation for case study areas for the final survey:

- Estonia, Tallinn University of Technology
- Finland, University of Lapland and University of Oulu
- Germany, TU Bergakademie Freiberg
- Poland, KGHM Cuprum Research & Development
- Zambia, University of Zambia

Each case study partner will analyse the data gathered during the first launch questionnaire survey, identify which questions are still relevant for the final survey, and upload the findings in the project's shared folder. In addition, each case study partner is responsible for making the questions more precise, preparing required guidelines for the audiences, and undertaking accurate communication strategies for the survey.

2.8.2 Data Management

The final questionnaire survey initiatives will adopt privacy by following the required national and European Union guidelines, procedures, and standards. All partners will abide by national and GDPR-related rules for protecting personal information. TU Bergakademie Freiberg, the University of Oulu, and the University of Lapland will manage and share the necessary case study region-specific data for partners involved in the final survey. Partners supervising activities will have access to data needed for analysis and reporting, including pseudonymisation or anonymisation, with the necessary level of privacy protection.

TU Bergakademie Freiberg, the University of Lapland, and the University of Oulu will coordinate data distribution and analysis. The other partners will only have access to the data from their responsible case study. Each partner will draft a GDPR-related "Data protection statement" unique to the case study location and survey, which they will then post on the websites related to the questionnaire surveys.

3 Launch of University Courses

3.1 Background Information

'European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)' is a series of online courses initiated by the AGEMERA project. Launched with five higher education institutions (HEIs), it was made available to the public on the OPAL online platform on March 4, 2024. ECRMs aimed to enhance understanding of CRMs and their role in everyday life. The first course of the series of courses results from close cooperation between AGEMERA and its university partners, where the latest information from the practical field is implemented into higher education. Designed initially for future engineers and scientists from TUBAF, TT, OU, UL and UNZA, it is open for anyone to register and access content, contributing to the EU's plans to develop a digital higher education environment as outlined in the Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027) (European Commission, n.d.). Due to its innovative organizational structure, the series of online courses serves as an early example of integrating MCs into TUBAF's educational system, promoting lifelong learning through easy access to high-quality educational content.

3.2 University Courses Platform and its' Features

TUBAF, as the lead partner in launching the university courses, created the framework and provided the platform and all the instructions and assistance needed for the involved HEIs to conduct the courses on OPAL together. The courses are taking place on OPAL due to its intuitive design and free access for anyone, regardless of their academic background or geographical location. OPAL serves several German HEIs as an online learning platform, as it is Saxony's central learning platform for organizing and conducting academic courses.

ECRMs are structured within OPAL modularly, as shown in Figure 24. ECRMs include a dedicated section that provides information on navigating the courses and frequently asked questions, visible to everyone, as a helpful aid to explain each course component.

Within ECRMs, participants can register as students or tutors, granting them different access rights. Tutors, for example, can upload content, whereas students cannot. However, sections and content become visible only after registration in one of these roles. A dedicated section with tutor profiles is included to help students learn more about the tutors' backgrounds before their presentations.

Live lectures are delivered in a virtual classroom, where several functions enable interactive participation. Tutors can upload presentations, and participants can send personal messages, share notes and engage in face-to-face interactions via microphone and video, depending on their willingness. These live lectures are recorded and stored on the VIMP video platform by TUBAF, allowing registered participants to review them later. Links to these recordings are uploaded within each chapter's 'Recorded (or Pre-Recorded) Session' section in OPAL.

Course content, such as lecture files, literature, and links, is organized by chapter and presentation date within course-specific sections. Registered representatives from the partnering HEIs (tutors) upload this content. Students can also upload assignments to the relevant folder within the online platform if requested.

Figure 24. Screenshot of the OPAL landing page of the 'European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)' course series

The course includes a certification of attendance (COA), which acts as a motivational reward for successful participants. To receive the COA, as shown in Figure 28, participants must complete an online pre-examination as part of performance assessments and provide feedback via an online questionnaire to the course responsible. All this takes place within OPAL without the necessity to register somewhere else.

One of the platform's most significant features is its open-access option with easy registration procedures. Anyone can complete the COA at any time, regardless of their academic background or geographical location, and can freely access the ECRMs course materials, including the recorded lecture videos, lecture materials, and additional information. OPAL automatically creates the COA when the respective person fulfils all requirements.

The COA is a prerequisite for taking a 90-minute graded online written exam as part of a higher-level performance assessment. Upon successfully completing the written exam and enrolment at TUBAF, participants are eligible to receive three ECTS credits.

3.3 Communication & Dissemination of the Courses

3.3.1 AGEMERA Website

As displayed in Figure 25, a dedicated section on the AGEMERA website was created to promote and circulate information about the university courses introduced for the AGEMERA project. This webpage overviews the courses' thematic focus and the involved HEIs. It also highlights the main benefits of enrolling, such as learning from home, access to interesting lectures, support through tutors, the inclusion of guest lecturers, attendance certification, and ECTS credits.

The screenshot shows the AGEMERA website landing page for university courses. The page features a navigation bar at the top with links for 'Who We Are', 'Our REEs', 'Skills and Resources', 'Media', and 'CONTACT US'. A prominent orange banner at the top reads 'Our platform is open now' with a 'Enroll here' button.

The main content area is titled 'University Courses: European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)'. It includes a paragraph explaining the EU's goal to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and the need for a steady supply of critical raw materials (CRMs). A photograph of a student with a backpack is shown on the right.

A 'Thematic focus' section highlights two categories: 'Rare earth elements (REEs)' and 'Battery raw materials (BRMs)'. Below this, it lists key points: 'And how...', 'They contribute to our modern lifestyles', 'They contribute to the green and digital transition', 'They impact the geopolitical landscape and can give birth to socio-environmental concerns', 'They are related to sustainable reporting standards: UNFC and UNSG', and 'Further geo-engineering information and economic and marketing aspects'.

The 'You should apply if...' section lists five criteria with checkmarks:

- You are a university student - all specializations are welcome
- You are curious to learn more about critical raw materials and why they are so important to our everyday life and overall economy
- You want to gain a better understanding of today's opportunities and challenges related to mineral exploration and mining in Europe
- You want to benefit from lectures taught by experts from reputable European institutions
- You want to learn about the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) and the UN Resource-Management System and why they are important

The 'Benefits:' section lists five advantages with star icons:

- Freedom to learn online, from the comfort of your home
- Access to specialized literature
- Support from a tutor
- Prominent guest speakers
- Certificate of attendance
- 3 ECTS upon completion

The 'Universities involved' section displays logos for TUBAF, TAL TECH, and other institutions. At the bottom, there are sections for 'Platform' (Opal - Diklungsportal Sachsen) and 'When?' (March 2024, examinations in April).

Figure 25. Screenshot of the landing page with the information on the university courses on the AGEMERA website

A direct link to register for the online course hosted on OPAL is implemented at the top of the webpage. By clicking the link, visitors are redirected to a second webpage titled "University Courses: How to Register," as shown in Figure 26. This web page includes a quick guide and detailed instructions on enrolling in OPAL. The registration process is nearly identical for tutors and students, and the comprehensive instructions ensure that even those unfamiliar with OPAL can successfully complete it.

Figure 26. Registration and enrolment details for the university courses on the AGEMERA website

3.3.2 Digital Media

A media kit (illustrated in Figure 27) containing informative texts and visuals was developed by GEO, the project's communication partner and TUBAF to promote and attract participants to the AGEMERA university courses across different digital media platforms. Having the importance of strategic timing in mind, a detailed proposal including a pre-planned timetable for using the media kit was communicated with the contributing HEIs (TUBAF, TT, UL, UO and UNZA) to ensure a coordinated and well-timed distribution of content, maximising outreach and impact.

Figure 27. A selection of visuals from the media kit which was prepared to disseminate the university courses

Based on the media kit, the contributing HEIs, TUBAF, TT, UO, UL and UNZA, used their organisations' digital media channels to disseminate the AGEMERA university courses to a wide range of people.

For instance, TUBAF promoted course enrolment by posting on Instagram's social media platform. In total, the dissemination on Instagram through TUBAF reached 2,304 individual accounts. The post received over 3,000 impressions; 72 people liked it, and 13 saved it. Additionally, TT shared information about university courses on the social media platform LinkedIn. TTs' several posts resulted in 3,518 impressions, 2,198 unique views, 54 reactions, 2 comments and 5 reposts.

GEO communicated information about the university courses through the project's profile on several social media platforms using the media kit. This effort resulted in 4,903 impressions and 244 engagements on LinkedIn, 319 impressions and 44 engagements on Facebook and 1,215 views with 47 engagements on X (formerly known as Twitter). A specific link (created through Bit.ly) was included in all the posts of the media kit, allowing us to track the number of users who clicked on it and opened the webpage of the courses, resulting in 158 engagements.

Partners from UL created an event notification for their website and stood in contact with the "Student Union", which promised to forward information about the courses to students via email.

3.3.3 Additional Communication & Dissemination Efforts

Next to the website and posts on social media networks, the contributing HEIs were requested to disseminate the courses through their staff to their students. Therefore, at TUBAF, the courses were advertised directly through messages from the course coordinators to more than 275 students enrolled on programs related to the mineral raw materials sector, part of TUBAFs' Faculty of Geosciences, Geoengineering and Mining. This included Dipl.-Ing. and Master's students from S-AMR, S-GEO, and S-MORE programs.

Furthermore, TUBAF contributed to the ProWissen booklet, highlighting the core aspects of the university courses. This booklet is a comprehensive resource where students can find information about courses offered at TUBAF. It is available both in [digital format](#) and as a printed version, handed out, for example, in TUBAF's cafeteria.

3.4 Contents and Structures of the Courses

The content is classified into information relevant to performance assessments and additional bonus content. The first seven chapters contain content relevant to performance assessments, named the main chapters. Content not relevant to performance assessments is stored within Chapter 8 and is aimed at people looking for additional information.

The courses cover different topics related to the mineral raw materials industry along the whole value chain, showcasing challenges and opportunities. The lectures incorporate geological and engineering information while addressing geopolitical, economic, marketing, social, and environmental aspects. Additionally, they provide information on the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDG) and significant international resource classification frameworks and systems, including the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) and the UN Resource Management System (UNRMS).

3.4.1 Main Chapters

Chapters 1 to 7 were presented throughout nine days, from March 04 until March 22, 2024. The details of each lecture day are displayed in Table 6 below.

Table 7. Main chapters of the ECRMs university courses

Number	Chapter	Lecture Topic	Schedules of the Live Lectures in 2024
1	Geology & Exploration of CRMs	Geology of CRMs in Africa (Zambia)	Monday, March 04, from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM CET
		Geology of CRMs in Europe	Tuesday, March 05, from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM CET
		Conventional Exploration Technologies for CRMs vs Minimal Invasive Exploration of CRMs	Wednesday, March 06, from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM CET
2	Geo-Politics & Challenges	The Green New Deal & CRMs	Thursday, March 07, from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM CET
3	Extraction of CRMs in a Global Environment	Mining in a Global Environment	Monday, March 18, from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM CET
4	Social Assessment	Social Assessment in Mining & Exploration	Thursday, March 21, from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM CET
5	Environmental Assessment	Environmental Impact Assessment in the Extractive Sector	Wednesday, March 20, from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM CET
6	Mineral Economics	Economic Resource Evaluation	Tuesday, March 19, from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM CET
7	International Frameworks	SDGs, UNRMS & UNFC	Friday, March 22, from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM CET

With the first lecture of Chapter 1, the course starts with covering the geology and locations of noteworthy CRM deposits, particularly REEs and BRMs in Africa (with a focus on Zambia).

In the second lecture of Chapter 1, the focus shifts to Europe, where attendees explore the diverse geological environments and various CRM deposits found across the continent. They gain insights into the historical context of European mining, current

mineral exploration efforts, and the strategic benefits of accessing domestic CRM sources to reduce dependence on imports.

In the third session, various methods for collecting data and exploring underground resources are described through a combination of input from academia and the involved industry partners. Conventional mineral exploration methods are compared to minimally invasive and innovative techniques for exploring mineral deposits. In particular, the technologies used and developed in the AGEMERA project for subsurface rock characterisation are covered. These technologies include density characterisation using muons, drones combining magnetic, radiometric and electromagnetic sensing and passive seismic. In addition, the course discusses how to process, combine and visualise the collected data using a graphical user interface. Factors such as time, depth penetration, area coverage, volume, associated costs and the level of detail are considered the upsides and downsides of conventional alternatives (Joutsenvaara et al., 2024).

In the second chapter, participants are not only introduced to the socio-economic, environmental and technical advantages and disadvantages of various underground exploration methods, but they also gain an understanding of the geopolitical landscape influencing the supply and demand of critical raw materials. They learn about the strategic approaches of major economies, such as the USA, EU, and China, as well as their key methods for addressing supply chain challenges and the increasing demand for CRMs. Given that CRMs are bound to a certain location, the importance of international collaboration and ethical sourcing in ensuring sustainable access to these materials is stressed.

Chapter three highlights international initiatives and examples of successful partnering networks in the mineral raw materials sector. It also covers responsible sourcing, the circular economy, and the significance of education and entrepreneurship for driving sector growth and sustainability. In that relation, it discusses the latest advancements and trends in the sector, including mining 4.0, big data, machine learning, digital twins, and remote sensing.

In the fourth chapter, the focus is on social aspects. International projects related to the sourcing of raw mineral materials necessitate comprehensive planning and stakeholder involvement, particularly regarding the local economic, environmental, and social context, to mitigate potential risks that could have a negative effect on the projected outcome. Business risk, in relation to mineral exploration, extends beyond geological and financial aspects; among the most significant risks the sector faces are social issues. Although mineral exploration often does not have a significant impact on the environment, it can create uncertainty about the locality's future and may indirectly affect investments in tourism or housing (Suopajarvi et al., 2022).

In addition to concepts like the Social Licence to Explore (SLE) and the Social Licence to Operate (SLO), the fifth chapter introduces participants to environmental topics, including environmental impact assessments (EIA) and related EU legislation such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and Natura 2000. These topics highlight the

importance of environmental and cultural considerations and provide examples of good business practices.

In the latter part of the lecture, through chapters six and seven, participants gain an understanding of the basics of mineral economics, resource evaluation, classification and resource management within the context of sustainable development, with practical examples from case studies. The lectures include an overview of standards from the Committee for Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards (CRIRSCO), which provides guidelines for disclosing reserves, resources and outcomes of mineral exploration to the public. Furthermore, the lectures explain the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) and its structure across different axes and the United Nations Resource Management System (UNRMS), including its purpose, desired outcomes, key definitions and toolkit concepts.

In the seventh chapter, participants receive a historical overview of sustainability, which begins with the pre-industrial era and encompasses developments during the industrialisation period. This historical overview also covers the contributions of early consciousness-raisers such as Colbert, Evelyn and von Carlowitz, who laid the foundation for the modern understanding of sustainability. The lecture introduces events that have further developed the idea of sustainable development, such as the publication of the Brundtland Report or the Earth Summit, which paved the way for adopting the SDGs. The lecture details the SDGs' characteristics, objectives, structure and the challenges associated with achieving them.

3.4.2 Bonus Chapter

After the lectures of the first seven chapters concluded, bonus presentations were held. These included five live sessions covering specific in-depth topics (Table 7).

Table 8. Bonus contents of the ECRMs courses

Number	Chapter	Lecture Topic	Schedules of the Live Lectures in 2024
8	Bonus Content	The AGEMERA Graphical User Interface	Monday, April 15, from 10:00 AM to 11:00 AM CET
8	Bonus Content	Muon-Based Density Characterization of Rocks	Tuesday, April 16, from 10:00 AM to 11:00 AM CET
8	Bonus Content	Q&A Session on International Reporting Standards	Wednesday, April 17, from 10:00 AM to 11:00 AM CET
8	Bonus Content	OECD Mining Regions and Cities initiative	Thursday, April 18, from 10:00 AM to 11:00 AM CET
8	Bonus Content	Multi-Sensing Drones: Combining Magnetic, Radiometric, and Electromagnetic Sensing for Subsurface Characterization	Friday, April 19, from 10:00 AM to 11:00 AM CET

The first session of the bonus content chapter included the AGEMERA Geo-Suite graphical user interface (GUI), one of AGEMERA's project's main outputs. The GUI collects, stores, analyses and visualises 2D and 3D time series data, which originates from innovative non-invasive geophysical survey methods. (AGEMERA, n.d.)

Among these technologies is muon-based density characterisation of rocks, which was addressed in the second session. Muography, also known as cosmic ray biography, is based on high-energy muons from cosmic rays, which pass through the earth at any given time, to image the internal density distribution of large geological formations. This method is cost-effective, time-efficient and has a minimal environmental footprint, all without being constrained by the specific characteristics of the medium. (Holma *et al.*, 2024)

During the third lecture, a question-and-answer session focused on international reporting standards. These included global standards such as the JORC Code, NI 43-101, the PERC Reporting Standard, and the UNFC. In collaboration with a specialist in the field, the session addressed participants' questions and provided guidance on how these different frameworks compare to each other.

The fourth presentation, part of the bonus content chapter, was held by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) on its Mining Regions and Cities Initiative. The OECD helps policymakers develop region-specific strategies that align with global energy goals and promote positive economic, social, and environmental outcomes in mineral-rich regions.

The fifth and final bonus lecture introduced multi-sensing drones, a technology utilised and further developed within the AGEMERA project. These drones collect magnetic, radiometric, and electromagnetic data for subsurface characterisation. The different operational principles and benefits, as well as downsides, compared to alternative options, were discussed.

3.5 Certification of Attendance, Performance Assessments & Feedback Received

As previously mentioned in section '3.2 University Courses Platform and its Features', a COA, displayed in Figure 28, was designed to certify the participation of successful students who passed the online performance assessment (in the form of an online pre-examination) and provided feedback through an online questionnaire. The certification process aims to ensure that students have properly understood the topics covered in the course. From the coordinator's perspective, the COA, serving as a motivational reward, ensures the collection of sufficient insights from participants. Based on the feedback, the coordinators can formulate the scope of improvement for future courses. After receiving the COA and enrolling in TUBAF, participants can participate in an online written examination to be eligible to receive 3 ECTS.

3.5.1 Template of the Certification of Attendance

The COA is designed to display all relevant aspects of the courses, as illustrated in Figure 28. A draft of the COA was created by TUBAF and reviewed by GEO. At the top, it features the logos of the AGEMERA project and the coordinating partner, TUBAF. The COA includes the course titles, the date of issuance, and the first and last name of the person who successfully completed the courses. It also contains a brief description of the courses and their learning outcomes. Additionally, there is an overview of the various topics covered and the prerequisites for receiving the COA. At the bottom, the signature of the responsible person is included, along with the logos of the different HEIs involved (TUBAF, TT, OU, UL, UNZA) and the main partners in issuing the COA (TUBAF and AGEMERA).

Figure 28. Template of the certification of attendance for the university courses

3.5.2 Online Pre-Examination

An online pre-examination was arranged for the student's performance assessment. The online pre-examination is a possibility for students to get a feeling of whether they are ready for the 90-minute, online, graded written examination and serves as a pre-requisite to receive the COA. The pre-examination covers 33 questions, created based on contents from all seven chapters and developed in collaboration with representatives of the partnering HEIs. To ensure that the OPAL system can automatically assess the pre-examination, the multiple-choice format was chosen, as OPAL does not support automated qualitative assessments. This way, the course is scalable to many participants without substantially increasing the operational workload of the course coordinators. Participants who do not pass the online pre-examination have two additional opportunities to retake it before receiving the COA.

3.5.3 Feedback from Students & Participants

An online questionnaire in OPAL was designed to receive participants' feedback and assess whether the course met its goals of enhancing the understanding of the importance of CRMs. The questions within the feedback questionnaire can be classified according to 8 different purposes, as displayed in Table 8. The questionnaire begins by collecting basic information about the participants, including their student status, university, study program and level of education, to learn about their background (in topic 1). Within topic 2, the questionnaire participants provide feedback on the course design, including their enrolment experience, navigation and preferences for online, physical or hybrid formats, and attendance at live virtual lectures. Participant and tutor engagement is assessed through questions about participants' perceptions of teaching and engagement in the third topic. The questionnaire also assesses people's expectations when they enrolled in the course to understand whether the course met those expectations and why they registered for the fourth topic. To determine whether the content presented is relevant to participants, the questionnaire asks in topic 5 about how novel or interesting the contents are to participants. Towards the end, data is collected on learning outcomes and whether the course effectively raised awareness about CRMs in topic 6. In addition to collecting information on how participants learned about the course, the survey conclusion sections (topic 7) also offer opportunities for other remarks and suggestions. The feedback questionnaire consists of a mix of quantitative and qualitative questions. Quantitative questions ask participants to respond to statements by selecting or rating predefined answers, using yes/no questions or Likert scales ranging from 1 to 5 or 1 to 7.

3.5.4 Online Written Examination

Completing the online pre-examination and the feedback questionnaire is required to qualify for the written online examination. The written examination is conducted once every year. Technical requirements to participate include downloading the web browser Google Chrome, having a webcam positioned to display the participants' hands during the exam, access to a device for scanning results (e.g., a scanner or phone as a backup) and ensuring the ability to log in to the online platform on both a desktop computer or laptop and a mobile phone as a backup. Students are advised to ensure they can log in

to OPAL on their devices before the examination day, as coordinators cannot address login issues on the exam day. The written examination is conducted online in virtual meeting rooms, separate from the virtual classroom used for lectures. Students joined online 30 minutes before the exam's start for the identification process and to ensure compliance with formal and technical requirements. Identification is performed using each person's student ID.

Table 9. Feedback questionnaire for the online courses (ECRMs)

Number	Topic	Subtopic
1	Background Information About Participants	Q1.1: Respondent's Nationality Q1.2: Enrolment at HEI Q1.3: Name of HEI (students only) Q1.4: Name of Study Program (students only) Q1.5: Type of Study Program (students only) Q1.6: Progress within the Study Program (students only)
2	Course Experience	Q2.1: Registration Process Q2.2: Course Navigation Q2.3: Willingness to Attend Online Course Again Q2.4: Ranking of Different Course Concepts Q2.5: Attendance at Live Presentations (Chapters 1 to 7) Q2.6: Attendance at Bonus Presentations (Chapter 8)
3	Participant Engagement	Q3.1: Opportunities for Engagement with Other Participants
4	Course Motivation and Expectations	Q4.1: Reasons for Attending the Course Q4.2: Expectations for the Course
5	Content Evaluation	Q5.1: Interest in Presented Contents Q5.2: Novelty of Presented Contents
6	Learning Outcomes	Q6.1: Time of First Introduction to CRMs Q6.2: Enhancement of Understanding of CRMs Q6.3: Additional Ways the Course Improved Knowledge
7	Marketing Data Collection	Q7.1: How Participants Heard About the Course Q7.2: Willingness to Attend Without ECTS Credits Q7.3: Suggestions for Course Improvement
8	Survey Conclusion	Q8.1: Missing Questions to be Included Q8.2: Additional Comments and Feedback

Participants can only be able to see themselves in the virtual meeting room and were unable to send private messages or use the public chat function. All participants were muted upon entry, but it was possible to unmute and to ask the coordinators questions. No external communication, assistance, or internet usage was permitted during the exam. After the identification process and explanation of rules, the coordinator made the PDF file of the exam available to students. Participants were instructed to handwrite their responses on paper, including their name and email address on each side of the sheets and then submit their results as a single file online in the designated upload folder. Uploaded files were named according to group, surname and version. Students

had 90 minutes to finish the written examination and an additional 15 minutes to upload their files. Similar to the online pre-examination, questions from each chapter were included and developed in collaboration with different presenters of the courses.

3.6 Key Outcomes

3.6.1 Results of the Communication & Dissemination Efforts

In the first term of the course, 73 people registered from over 25 nations. Based on the e-mail addresses used by the registered people, conclusions were drawn regarding their background. Out of the 73 people who registered, a great majority of the people (50) are students of TUBAF. Out of the 50 participants from TUBAF, 41 are part of TUBAF's Faculty of Geosciences, Geoengineering and Mining. Seven people enrolled from the Faculty of Materials Science and Technology and two from the Faculty of Mechanical, Process, and Energy Engineering. Two people registered for the course from OU, three from TT, and one from UL. Quantifying the number of students from UNZA was impossible, as they seem to use private email accounts. However, several students later identified themselves as students from UNZA during the courses. In addition, participants used email addresses that could be assigned to external organisations, partner companies of the project, and HEIs that were not affiliated with the AGEMERA project.

3.6.2 Evaluation of the Online Pre-Examination

The online pre-examination, feedback questionnaire, and COA were launched on April 22, 2024, on OPAL. The online pre-examination consists of 33 questions, each worth one point, for a total score of 33. In the first term of the course, 33 participants took the online pre-examination, achieving an average score of 27.59 out of 33, corresponding to 83.61%. All 33 participants passed the pre-examination with a minimum of 13.2 points (40%) required to pass. The online pre-examination features questions on each chapter, developed in collaboration with the various presenters and is conducted in a multiple-choice format. The average time to fulfil the pre-examination was 24:02 minutes, while participants had a maximum of 45 minutes for completion.

3.6.3 Evaluation of the Feedback Questionnaire

Among 33 of the 73 people who registered for ECRMs completed the online feedback questionnaire, which is available in OPAL. The results from the feedback questionnaire were taken directly from OPAL. The results were interpreted and allocated to the different topics, as displayed in Table 8.

Topic 1 Background Information About Participants

In Q1.1, 33 participants from 21 different nations were identified. Among the 33 respondents, in Q1.2, almost all (93.94%) indicated that they are enrolled in a higher education institution (HEI), while only a small proportion (6.06%) are not.

Of the 31 people enrolled in higher education, the majority (80.65%) mentioned in Q1.3 that they are enrolled at TUBAF. A total of 30 participants provided information about their study programs as part of Q1.4. Almost all (96.67%) are enrolled in programs related to geosciences, spanning nine different programs. The largest group is enrolled in

TUBAF's master's program in Sustainable Mining and Remediation Management (33.33%), followed by 20.00% in the master's program in Advanced Mineral Resource Development.

Of the 31 participants enrolled at HEIs, most (74.19%) were selected in Q1.5 to be part of a master's program. The remaining respondents are enrolled in PhD programs (12.90%), bachelor's programs (9.68%), or diploma programs (3.23%). This means most respondents (90.32%) are part of postgraduate programs.

According to the answers to Q1.6, 58.06% of the 31 higher-education participants are close to completing their studies. Another 38.71% are in the middle of their studies, while only a small proportion (3.23%) are at the beginning.

Topic 2 Course Experience

Regarding the course experience, a majority of the 33 respondents (69.70%) strongly agreed in Q2.1 that it was easy to register for the pilot course. An additional 24.24% agreed with the statement, while 6.06% were neutral. No one disagreed or strongly disagreed. Most respondents (72.73%) also strongly agree that the course was easy to navigate in Q2.2. A further 15.15% agreed, while 12.12% were neutral. No one disagreed or strongly disagreed. 87.88% of people gave positive feedback (equivalent to 'strongly agree' or 'agree'). Approximately three-quarters (75.76%) of the 33 respondents selected in Q2.3 that they were very likely to retake an online course after having visited ECRMs. Another 24.24% thought it was possible. None of the respondents said it was unlikely or very unlikely. 100% of people gave positive feedback (equivalent to answering 'very likely' or 'likely').

In Q2.4, respondents were asked to rate different course concepts. Among the 33 respondents, 51.52% rated online lectures as the best concept, and 42.42% rated them as good. In total, 93.94% provided positive feedback (equivalent to answering 'best' or 'good').

Regarding physical lectures, 33.33% of the participants rated them as the best concept, and 15.15% rated them as good. 48.48% gave positive feedback ('best' or 'good'), while 36.36% rated them as an average course concept. A small proportion rated physical lectures as bad (3.03%) or the worst teaching concept (6.06%).

For hybrid lectures, 33.33% rated them as the best concept, and 36.36% rated them as a good concept. In total, 69.69% of respondents provided positive feedback. More than a fifth (21.21%) rated hybrid lectures as an average course concept, and only a small proportion (3.03%) rated hybrid lectures as the worst teaching method.

In Q2.5, participants were asked to estimate how many of the live lectures they attended in their presence. Out of the 33 respondents, just over a quarter (27.27%) reported attending 100% of the lectures in Chapters 1 to 7 in Q2.5. A larger quantity (42.42%) selected that they attended between 76% and 99% of the lectures. Additionally, 12.12% attended between 51% and 75% of the live presentations, while 15.15% attended less than 25% of the sessions.

Regarding the live presentations of the bonus content chapter, in Q2.6, none of the respondents (0%) indicated that they attended 100% of them. Almost a quarter (24.24%) joined between 76% and 99% of the presentations, 9.09% attended between 51% and 75%, 6.06% chose 50%, 9.09% attended between 25% and 49%, and 27.27% of the respondents chose less than 25%. Additionally, 24.24% indicated that they did not attend any of the live presentations of the bonus content chapter.

Topic 3 Participant Engagement

Out of 33 respondents, 24.24% strongly agreed that participants have the opportunity to engage with other people in the online course, while 18.18% agreed and 45.45% were neutral. Additionally, 9.09% disagreed. Overall, respondents were satisfied with the engagement of the tutors, as indicated in Q 3.1. Of 33 respondents, 57.58% strongly agreed that the tutors were open to engaging, 27.27% agreed, 9.09% were neutral, and 3.03% disagreed. Most respondents (60.61%) strongly agreed that the tutors were competent, 27.27% agreed, and 9.09% selected neutral.

Topic 4 Course Motivation and Expectations

Respondents were asked why they attended the course through an open-ended question in Q4.1. Responses range from personal interest to further development in their academic or already professional career. For instance, one respondent, a consultant active in the mineral raw materials sector, sees the course as an opportunity to learn more about the industry and the EU Critical Raw Materials Act. Another respondent appreciated the chance to learn from international speakers. Several participants mentioned that the course was an excellent opportunity to enhance their knowledge, gather information and insights into different concepts and revise their existing knowledge about CRMs, REEs and BRMs. Master's and doctoral students mentioned that the course content was relevant to their thesis topics. In Q4.2, participants were asked if the course met their expectations. The trend shows that the course did meet respondents' expectations: out of 33 respondents, 57.58% strongly agree and 42.42% agree. No respondent selected 'neutral', 'disagree', or 'strongly disagree'.

Topic 5 Content Evaluation

Respondents were asked to rate different presentations based on their personal interest, using a scale ranging from 'most interesting', 'interesting', 'neutral', 'not interesting' to 'least interesting'. While individual preferences varied, typical values for 'not interesting' are 0%, 3.03%, or 6.06% and 'least interesting' does not exceed 3.03%. The average value for 'neutral' is 13.13%.

The average sum of responses for 'most interesting' or 'interesting' comprised approximately 80%.

Participants were also asked about the novelty of the content in the individual presentations. They could choose from 'completely new', 'the majority of content is new to me', 'the amount of new and known content is balanced', 'the majority of content is known to me' and 'nothing is new to me'.

The average responses show that participants think the material is new in general; 35% of respondents say it was 'completely new', and 27.71% selected 'the majority of content is new to me', resulting in 62.71%. Furthermore, according to 22.71% of respondents, 'the amount of new and known content is balanced'. Meanwhile, the combined average for the categories 'nothing is new to me' and 'the majority of content is known to me' is 8.12%.

The responses show an overall tendency in a positive direction towards the material being viewed as novel, with subjects related to the technologies used in the AGEMERA project receiving the highest ratings. Content on multi-sensing drones is rated as 'completely new' by 37.50% and 'the majority of content is new to me' by 40.62%. Similarly, 37.50% of respondents see the presentation on passive seismic analysis for subsurface characterisation as 'completely new'. In addition, 46.88% say that 'most content is new to me'. The presentation on muon-based density characterisation of rocks received 'completely new' ratings from 62.50% and 'the majority of content is new to me' from 28.12%.

Topic 6 Learning Outcomes

In Q6.1, respondents were asked when they were first introduced to CRMs. Most respondents (71.43%) indicated that they were introduced to CRMs before registering for the course. Almost a third (28.57%) heard about CRMs for the first time during the course. Subsequently, in Q6.2, respondents rated their agreement on whether the course enhanced their understanding of various CRM-related topics. 86.65% of the feedback was positive ('strongly agree': 48.86%; 'agree': 37.78%). On average, 11.36% of respondents were neutral, and only 1.7% provided negative feedback ('strongly disagree': 0%; 'disagree': 1.87%) regarding the course's ability to enhance their understanding of various topics related to CRMs. In Q6.3 of the feedback questionnaire, participants were asked how else ECRMs improved their knowledge about CRMs beyond the previously mentioned learning outcomes. Below, a selection of received responses is displayed:

- *“The process of how they are extracted and processed was new to me and I learned a lot about the different CRMs and their economic and strategic importance.”*
- *“revisit the course and research further”*
- *“It is my first exposure to mineral resources to African continent. Second thing, the context of policies and regulations and amendment to CRMs was something I havent explored until before this course.”*
- *“I had a realization about the vast spread of the field.”*
- *“to see different sides of the industry whas quite beneficial”*
- *“how important these materials are to key sectors of life.”*

- *“A great update to know what's going on. Some stuff are not common in normal classes, so It was great.”*
- *“There was a lot of new things to learn”*
- *“This course enhanced my understanding of REE and other things related to mining exploration etc”*

Topic 7 Marketing Data Collection

Respondents were asked in Q7.1 how they found out about the course. The most significant proportion (50%) heard about ECRMs through their universities' internal communication outlets, such as the daily e-mail bulletin. The second largest group (25%) were contacted directly by the course organisers (or university staff). In addition, 14.29% were informed by colleagues and friends, while 10.71% found out about the courses on the AGEMERA account on LinkedIn's social media platform. Most respondents (84.85%) indicated in Q7.2 that they would attend the course regardless of the ECTS credits offered. A smaller percentage (15.15%) selected that they would not participate in the course if it would not be possible to achieve ECTS credits.

Topic 8 Survey Conclusion

Respondents were asked whether they had any additional comments or anything else they would like to share as feedback. Many people left the question blank or answered 'no'; some used the question to thank the organisers.

3.6.4 Evaluation of the Certification of Attendance

Of the 73 students who signed up for the first ECRMs courses, 33 students showed dedication by finishing the online pre-examination and the feedback questionnaire on the ECRMs portal in OPAL. They successfully obtained a COA by demonstrating their knowledge of the individual course topics and active participation in providing feedback. Through the COA, students have valuable proof that is usable in their academic and professional development. This certificate is an essential step for students to be eligible to be accepted to attend the online written exam, a pre-requisite for obtaining a 3.0 ECTS issued by TUBAF.

3.6.5 Evaluation of the Online Written Examination

An online written examination was held on May 03, 2024, and was open to all participants aiming to obtain 3 ECTS credits from the European Credit Transfer System that have achieved the COA. Successful completion of both the online pre-examination and the feedback questionnaire by May 2, 2024, was required to qualify for the written online examination. In total, all 19 people who registered also successfully passed the written examination. The online written examination will be repeated in the first half of 2025.

3.7 Improvement Scope and Outlook for Future Courses

3.7.1 Improvement Scope

With an average attendance rate of 35.62% among registered participants for the live lectures of chapters 1 to 7, the overall attendance is considered low. However, the attendance rate for the live presentations was relatively high among those who achieved the COA. Specifically, 69.69% of the 33 respondents indicated that they attended 76% to 100% of all chapters 1 to 7 presentations.

The non-mandatory presentations had lower attendance rates than the presentations of chapters 1 to 7, with an average attendance rate of 10.41% of the 73 registered participants.

According to the feedback questionnaire results, only 24.24% joined between 76% and 99% of the presentations in person, and 27.27% of the respondents chose less than 25%. Additionally, 24.24% indicated that they did not join any of the live presentations of chapter 8.

Different respondents to the feedback questionnaire mentioned that they missed the live presentations due to time differences or their option to combine the presentation with their studies or jobs. However, the recorded presentations (as of June 26, 2024) have shown that participants actively (re-) watched the recordings, as 656 views were achieved.

- Based on the comparably low attendance rate of bonus presentations (Chapter 8), all future efforts will focus on mandatory content for performance assessments.
- Since attendees come from various study programs and geographical locations, finding a schedule that suits everyone is impossible. However, since most registrants are from TUBAF, particularly the S-MORE study program, scheduling the courses to align with this program's timetable could help minimise conflicts and benefit the attendance rates of live lectures.

Out of 33 respondents to the feedback questionnaire, 24.24% strongly agreed that participants have the opportunity to engage with other people in the online course, while 18.18% agreed and 45.45% were neutral. Compared to other answers to questions, the number of people who chose 'neutral' is comparably high.

- To improve engagement, satisfaction, and attendance rates for live lectures and potentially increase student numbers, a hybrid lecture framework will be introduced in collaboration with partnering HEIs with access to the necessary infrastructure.
- In addition, the feasibility of implementing a case study to make the courses more interactive will be explored.

Conducting hybrid lectures allows people to join a real classroom while simultaneously livestreaming the session to a virtual classroom. While not all partners can fully implement this concept, it could be partially adopted by those with the technical equipment available. This strategy would require additional effort, but it could satisfy those who provided negative or neutral feedback in the questionnaire regarding engagement possibilities. Tutors would benefit from direct interaction and quicker feedback, and students who prefer in-person lectures might be more open to attending.

Live events at partner universities could attract attention and increase the visibility of the courses, encouraging people who are unsure whether they should register for the courses and resulting in more registered students.

The integration of a case study could increase student interest and registration numbers. Since the COA is designed to be obtainable at any time of the year, the case study should be structured accordingly. The feasibility of integrating a case study will be examined before the second iteration of the courses.

More students could be reached by directly contacting them through announcements in lectures or messages from lecturers. Word-of-mouth was an indirect method of attracting students, where students informed their peers about the course. Therefore, the dissemination strategy for future classes should include calls to action that encourage people to tell their friends about the courses offered via AGEMERA.

- The evaluation revealed that many respondents had learned about the courses through their universities' communication channels. This highlights the importance of all involved HEIs focusing on the dissemination channels/methods their students actively subscribe to.
- For example, while platforms like LinkedIn may attract working professionals, university newsletters seem to be more effective in reaching actual students.

3.7.2 Summary

Based on the feedback questionnaire results concerning the registration process, course navigation and structure, and the positive indication by participants that they would be open to attending an online course like ECRMs again, no significant structural changes will be made for the next stage of the HEI courses. The contents will focus on sessions mandatory for performance assessments, hybrid courses or a case study might be introduced, and communication efforts shall be improved.

The pilot launch of the AGEMERA university courses (ECRMs) effectively introduced the challenges and opportunities of the mineral raw materials sector, focusing on CRMs, to a broad audience from over 25 nations. Respondents to the feedback questionnaire were satisfied with attending ECRMs, as the course significantly increased their understanding and knowledge about CRMs. The positive feedback indicates that the courses can significantly increase participants' understanding and knowledge about CRMs. However, most respondents to the feedback questionnaire were in the middle or advanced stages of postgraduate programs and had a background in raw materials. The trends from the feedback questionnaire evaluation show that the course met the participant's expectations, including tutors' engagement and competencies, with most content rated as very interesting or novel. Subjects related to the technologies used in the AGEMERA project, such as multi-sensing drones, passive seismic analysis for subsurface characterisation, muon-based density characterisation and the graphical user interface, received exceptionally high ratings, filling educational gaps with the most recent information from the industry and research.

4 Organisation of Public Awareness Events

4.1 Background Information

The planning and execution of public awareness campaigns, workshops, and seminars focused on critical metals and minerals. With an emphasis on meaningful conversations, these events, aimed at university students and the general public, seek to promote inclusive dialogue where stakeholders' perspectives are heard. A communication strategy has been created to ensure more engagement initiatives and can be a guideline at future events. Furthermore, questionnaires were designed before and after the event to compare and assess the degrees of social acceptance and public knowledge, and certificates of attendance were prepared and planned to be provided.

4.2 Communication Strategy Development

One of the main objectives of developing communication strategies in task 2.4 of the WP2 is the successful development, planning, and execution of workshops, seminars, and public awareness events regarding critical minerals and metals. The strategies aim to get participants interested in the arranged events in the task, ensure event information is widely distributed, and prepare the audience for such events. Engaging and attractive content and ensuring various views are crucial to improving the participants' knowledge at such events, which the WP5 leaders in the project support.

4.2.1 Prior Considerations During the Planning Phase

Before developing or organising workshops, seminars and public awareness activities, defining and segmenting the target audience into categories such as students, professionals, community members, legislators, environmentalists, and other relevant stakeholders is extremely important. By creating concise and engaging messages and explaining the importance of critical minerals and metals, attendees should emphasise how they would benefit from the event. To increase audience interest, highly interactive sessions with panel discussions, questions, and answers highlighting the importance of participants' roles in the events are advisable. Task 2.4 considers that active participation and fruitful discussion is the key to the success of its events.

Different engaging tools, such as Mentimeter, Slido, Poll Everywhere, etc., can engage the public with real-time discussion and provide opinions on specific topics. In addition, hands-on exercises can be conducted in seminars or workshops, where participants can brainstorm the criticality and various uses of critical raw materials in everyday life. To make the content more engaging, various multimedia tools, such as animations, movies, infographics, and PowerPoint presentations, should be used to show the adaptability and modernity of the event initiatives.

4.2.2 Outreach Initiatives

A multi-channel marketing strategy is proposed to reach the intended participants of the events. Social media platforms, email newsletters, community centres, local newspapers, and radio stations are typical channels to reach potential participants. The

projects and event organising partners' social media accounts, such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, and YouTube, are central platforms for advertising and promoting the planned seminar, workshops or public awareness event. Sending press releases regarding public awareness events to local and national media can help increase event outreach and inform targeted potential participants in parallel to the daily, weekly or monthly newsletters.

For outreach of such public events, the marketing campaign is suggested to be organised in three stages: (i) start a social media campaign six months before the event, send emails or information according to a schedule, and start community outreach; (ii) advertise through community boards, distribute training materials, and start registration at least three months before the event and finally, (iii) a month before the event, increase social media activity, share speaker profiles, and send reminder emails.

4.2.3 Summary and Follow-up Information

Publishing a summary of the event, including key takeaways, on the organising partner's and project's website and social media can enhance the effectiveness and success of the events. Feedback questionnaires on the event's effectiveness and knowledge improvement on critical raw materials will be collected from the participants after or at the last stage of the event. Information about upcoming events and developments related to essential minerals and sustainability can help to keep continuous contact with potential participants. A certificate of participation is also planned for such events on Task 2.4 to enhance the chance of engagement and interest provided after the events end.

4.3 Workshop, Seminar and Public Events

4.3.1 Overall Overview

The AGEMERA initiative continuously developed and organised public awareness campaigns through public events, seminars, and workshops on raw materials in several European sites (Table 9). There were two workshops, three seminars, and three public events. The purpose of these events was to involve a range of target audiences, such as students, professionals in the industry, members of civil society, and citizens.

Six residents attended a public event UL arranged in Finland to get local perspectives for the AGEMERA pilot questionnaire research. Thirty doctorate candidates and civil society representatives were introduced to the AGEMERA project through an online seminar hosted by UL. LAT and RAD organized two separate seminars. One seminar gathered twelve industry and business partners, and the other seminar hosted fifty citizens, where LAT and RAD discussed exploration work and the EU Critical Raw Materials Act in Kuusamo, Finland.

A workshop at TT in Pärnu County, Estonia, aimed to increase the knowledge of forty-nine Valga high school students on CRM. BAS organised a public awareness campaign in Bulgaria focusing on the AGEMERA project and strategic and critical raw materials for civil society. Eight members of civil society participated in a workshop at TalTech

Mektory, Estonia, where the topic of mineral commodities and, specifically, "Where does the fork come from?" was discussed.

Table 10. Organised public events, seminars and workshops in the project

Date	Type	Involved Partner	Venue / Place	Covered Topics	Target Group	Participants
17.01. 2023	Public Event	UL	Finland	AGEMERA pilot questionnaire study: What local people think	Citizens	6
19.01. 2023	Seminar	UL	Online	AGEMERA project to the doctoral candidates	Civil Society	30
11.10. 2023	Seminar	LAT, RAD	Kuusamo, Finland	Exploration work and results, EU Critical Raw Materials Act	Industry, business partners	12
10.20 23	Seminar	LAT, RAD	Kuusamo, Finland	Exploration work and results, EU Critical Raw Materials Act	Citizens	50
30 - 31.10. 2023	Public Event	UO	Rovaniemi, Finland	AGEMERA project, panel, speech, handouts	Wider Audience	120
9.04. 2024	Workshop	TT	TalTech, Pärnu County, Estonia	To raise awareness of CRM for high school students in Valga	Civil Society	49
11 - 12.05. 2024	Public Event	BAS	Bulgaria	AGEMERA project and critical and strategic raw materials (CSR)	Civil Society	-
6.06. 2024	Workshop	TT	TalTech Mektory, Estonia	Role of mineral commodities in the EU: Where does the fork come from?	Civil Society	8

Several target groups, including citizens, members of civil society, business professionals, and students, attended and participated in discussions at these public events, seminars, and workshops.

4.3.2 Engagement and Visual Highlights

Latitude 66 Cobalt and Radai arranged three events in October 2023, including one for the media and professional stakeholders, including the Geological Survey of Finland (GTK) and EIT Raw Materials. Later, articles on the planned drone test flights appeared in local and regional newspapers in November and December 2023.

Two separate seminars were organised in Kuusamo, which drew about fifty people from outlying areas (Figure 29-30) and industry and business partners. These two-hour interactive events included coffee talks, talks about ongoing exploration projects and their findings, explanations of the EU Critical Raw Materials Act and how it affects national laws, and in-depth drone demos.

The communication coordinator of Latitude 66 Cobalt, Jussi Lähde, notes that the local population has reacted well to drone surveys. He emphasises the significance of social acceptance, the AGEMERA initiative's primary goal.

Figure 29. Highlights from the first event for media and other professional stakeholders on October 11th by Latitude 66 and Radai (Hannamari Pietilä, Latitude 66 Cobalt Oy)

Figure 30. Highlights from the first event for media and other professional stakeholders on October 11th by Latitude 66 and Radai (Hannamari Pietilä, Latitude 66 Cobalt Oy)

4.4 Questionnaire and Certificate of Attendance

4.4.1 Questionnaire Implementation

Preparing and executing a systematic questionnaire data collection process at the start and end of an organised seminar, workshop, or public awareness event on critical raw materials is necessary to obtain insightful participant feedback. The process can begin with creating a list of questions that complement the goals and format of the organised event. Questions might address what participants expect from the events, what the participants currently know about critical raw materials, and what the expectations are from the events. Based on audience preferences and event logistics, the organising partner may choose the format, number of questions, and means of collection, which may be paper-based or digital questionnaire style.

The goal of the questionnaire should be explained, along with guidelines for filling it out to the participants, and participants should be made aware that their answers will remain anonymous and confidential according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Additionally, reminding attendees to fill out the post-event questionnaire survey is essential. Next, the questionnaires might be electronically gathered or collected through specific collecting stations, depending on the survey type. All participant questionnaire responses must be gathered securely. Then, the collected response data could be used to identify the spot patterns, knowledge gaps,

and potential scope of development areas of further events. Quantifying feedback, understanding of participants' critical raw material knowledge, and event effectiveness can be done by evaluating with appropriate statistical methods by the organising partners.

4.4.1.1 Questionnaire template to be used at the beginning of the event

- Age, gender, education
- How would you explain your current level of knowledge about critical raw materials?
- What comes to mind when you hear 'critical raw materials'?
- Are you aware of any current events or issues related to critical raw materials?
- How do critical raw materials impact our daily lives and the economy?
- Can you name any critical raw materials and their common uses?
- How do critical raw materials affect our economy and technological advancements?
- Do you think ethical concerns are associated with mining and processing such materials?
- What are your thoughts on the environmental impact of critical raw material exploration and extraction?
- What industries do you know that are heavily dependent on critical raw materials?
- What do you expect to learn from today's events?

4.4.1.2 Questionnaire template to be used at the end of the event

- What was the most surprising fact you learned about critical raw materials today?
- How can we improve the sustainability of critical raw material usage in our industries?
- What steps can we take to ensure a secure supply of critical raw materials in the future?
- How will today's information influence your personal or professional decisions?
- What role can individuals play in ensuring the responsible use of critical raw materials?
- How can businesses and governments collaborate to secure a stable supply of these materials?

- What actions are necessary to raise public awareness about the importance of critical raw materials?
- What innovative technologies or methods did you learn about that could help discover and extract critical raw materials?
- Do you plan to find out more about the topic in the future?
- Would you recommend this event to your friends and family?

4.4.2 Certificate of Attendance

The organising partners' responsibilities in giving certification of attendance to attendees of workshops, seminars, and public awareness events have been identified under task 2.4 and consist of many steps. A template for a certificate has been produced and will be distributed to the partners involved in the task (Figure 31) in request. The event title, date, venue, and organising partner are editable in this digital certificate template.

Figure 31. Certificate of attendance template to be provided to the attendees of workshops, seminars, and public awareness events

There have been a few recommendations regarding how the organising partner should provide the attendees with their certificate of attendance. At the certificate, it is crucial to emphasise the significance and focus of the events and the topics/themes discussed at the organised workshop, seminar, or public event. Include any hand-in activities that are undertaken as well. Signatures strengthen the certificate's authenticity from a critical organising partner and/or project coordinator member. Additionally, the certificates are planned to be given out at the end of the event in printed in hand or by post or digital form via email, along with the addition of the organisation or institution's logos.

4.5 Plan for Public Awareness Events

Several public awareness events are planned to increase knowledge of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) among different target groups through the AGEMERA project (Table 10). TT and UO are organising a teacher training session at UO that will target civil society and focus on the role of CRMs and the EU Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA) in daily life and society. Attendance will be recorded by providing certificates of attendance from the event. TT will organise an online teacher training webinar, in which civil society will be another focus group. Furthermore, TT will hold a workshop for policymakers, employees, entrepreneurs, and members of civil society at the Baltic Sustainability Festival at Põhjala Factory in Tallinn, Estonia.

A public discussion about CRMs and the AGEMERA project will be held in Bulgaria by BAS, with a focus on civil society. In Rovaniemi, Finland, LAT will host a public event focusing on CRMs and exploration. The event is intended for the local population and will provide certificates of attendance. These gatherings involve a range of target audiences, such as local community members, entrepreneurs, legislators, and employees. The webinars and seminars prepare educators to talk about CRMs and their place in society. For a broad audience, the workshop during the Baltic Sustainability Festival will offer practical learning opportunities. The public gatherings in Finland will showcase how the AGEMERA project has advanced our knowledge of and application for CRMs.

Table 11. Planned public awareness events for the AGEMERA project

Date	Type	Involved Partner	Venue / Place	Covered Topics	Target Group	Certificate of Attendance
27 & 29.08.2024	Seminar	TT & UO	UO	Teacher training to raise awareness about CRM and CRMA and their role in everyday life and society	Civil Society	Yes
xx.09.2024	Webinar	TT	Online	Teacher training	Civil Society	TBD
10-12.10.2024	Workshop	TT	Põhjala Factory, Tallinn, Estonia	A three-day Baltic sustainability festival where TT will conduct a workshop for CRM for visitors	Civil society, Entrepreneurs, policymakers, employees	TBD
22.04.2025	Public Event	BAS	Bulgaria	AGEMERA project and CRMs	Civil Society	TBD
xx.10.2024	Public Event	LAT	Rovaniemi, Finland	Exploration, CRMs	Local People	Yes

TBD = To Be Determined

5 Conclusion

The success and extent of improvements on a few of the WP2 activities of the AGEMERA project are highlighted in this second-year evaluation report. Even though the questionnaire survey produced data-driven information that would help researchers create well-informed policy recommendations and promote sustainable development, at the same time, the overall survey experience would serve as a reference for future enhancements in comparable initiatives for the following year. Simultaneously, an international audience was successfully engaged, and the EU's digital education objectives were advanced with the launch of the online courses "European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)," which were produced in collaboration with multiple HEIs partners. However, it has also shown potential for greater efficacy in educational projects to improve understanding of essential basic materials.

Furthermore, by fostering conversations amongst many stakeholders, WP2's public awareness initiatives, workshops, and seminars have increased community involvement and comprehension of critical raw materials. These initiatives show AGEMERA's dedication to sustainability and community involvement and helped the researchers create a more practical communication plan and ongoing assessment.

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